

Effect of fungicides (in vitro) on the growth of *Trichoderma harzianum* (Th) and *Rhizoctonia solani* (Rs)^a and disease severity^b of ShB.

Fungicide	Dose (%)	% inhibition of Th (mean)	% inhibition of Rs (mean)	Disease score	
				A (in vivo test I)	B (in vivo test II)
Atemi 50 SL	0.2	77.1 cd	75.1 de	3.7 a	4.3 b
Atemi 50 SL	0.1	31.8 b	49.0 c	5.0 bc	5.6 d
Bavistin 50 WP	0.1	79.5 cd	71.1 d	3.7 a	4.3 b
Bavistin 50 WP	0.05	65.1 c	53.4 c	4.3 ab	5.0 c
Contaf 5 EC	0.2	92.0 d	88.8 f	3.0 a	3.6 a
Contaf 5 EC	0.1	74.5 cd	71.7 d	4.3 ab	5.0 c
Indofil M-45	0.25	69.1 c	75.1 d	4.3 ab	5.6 d
Indofil M-45	0.125	48.4 bc	22.5 b	5.7 c	7.0 e
Hinosan 50 EC	0.1	43.4 bc	84.1 ef	3.7 a	3.6 a
Hinosan 50 EC	0.05	8.0 a	78.4 de	4.1 a	3.6 a
Rhizolex 50 WP	0.2	77.2 cd	72.7 d	4.3 ab	3.6 a
Rhizolex 50 WP	0.1	59.9 c	58.0 c	5.0 bc	5.0 c
Validacin 3L	0.2	76.4 cd	87.6 f	3.0 a	3.6 a
Validacin 3L	0.1	41.6 bc	54.5 c	5.0 bc	4.3 b
Control	-	0 a	0 a	8.3 d	8.3 f
Standard check	10 ⁶ conidia mL ⁻¹	-	-	-	5.6 d
LSD (0.05)		15.82	7.17	0.39	0.51
CV (%)		15.34	9.1	11.56	14.7

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. All data are means of three replications. ^b Scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice scale* 0-9. 1988.

were used and the plants were artificially inoculated with *R. solani*. Five sprays were done at weekly intervals beginning from the first appearance of the disease after 7 d of

inoculation. Contaf (0.2%) and Validacin (0.2%) showed the lowest disease severity, followed by Atemi (0.2%), Bavistin (0.1%), and Hinosan (0.1 and 0.05%) (see table).

In the second trial (B), the above treatments were used in combination with spray of the antagonist (Th) (106 conidia mL⁻¹). The sprays were initiated with the respective fungicides as the disease appeared and after. Thus, out of five sprays, two sprays were made with the antagonist (see table). An additional treatment (standard check) was included in this test where all five sprays were done with the antagonist alone. In this second field test (B), Th alone suppressed the disease compared with the unprotected control. The lowest disease severity was recorded when Th was combined with Contaf (0.2%), Hinosan (0.1 and 0.05%), Rhizolex (0.2%), and Validacin (0.2%). The combined treatment of Hinosan (0.05%) with the biocontrol agent was found to be an exception and Hinosan (0.05%) in both the experiments controlled the disease. As the effect of Hinosan (0.05%) on Th had been documented in an earlier experiment, it is suggested for inclusion in the integrated pest management strategy to control ShB. ■

Integrated pest management – insects

Record of *Aspergillus terreus* Thom. on rice grasshopper *Hieroglyphus banian* (F.) in India

R. Parthasarathy and P. Narayanasamy, Vector Pathology Laboratory, Entomology Department, Annamalai University, Annamalainagar 608002, Tamil Nadu, India

In a series of surveys on fungal diseases of rice insects in general and leafhopper in particular during the 1996 samba season (October through February) at Annamalainagar, 40% of the rice grasshopper (*Hieroglyphus banian* [F.]) population was found to be infected with a fungal pathogen.

Nymphs and adults were diseased. The cadavers were dull and brownish yellow and were seen holding the rice culms with their legs, with the insects' heads pointing toward the shoot tips (see figure). Abundant mycelial growth

***Aspergillus terreus* infecting the final nymphal instar of rice grasshopper.**

was observed at the intersegmental regions of the thorax and the abdomen but not the head capsule. On continued exposure to sunlight, the cadavers dried and the fungal matrix withered off.

The cadavers were gathered from the field, surface-sterilized with 0.1% HgCl₂ for 1-2 min, and washed in sterile water. The organism was inoculated in Sabouraud maltose agar

(SMA) medium on petri plates and incubated at 25±1 °C for 15 d. The fungal colonies appeared 5 d after inoculation and the culture was initially pale yellow or bright yellow, and ultimately deep brown.

Pathogenicity testing of the fungus isolated was done by spraying its spore suspension (107 spores mL⁻¹) over nymphs (second- and third-instar) and adults caged separately on IR50 rice plants grown in pots. The experiment was replicated three times using 10 insects replication⁻¹ and three replications of a control receiving plain water spray. Mean mortality of the grasshoppers was recorded as 85%, in 4-5 d after spraying (see table). The fungus from the diseased cadavers was reisolated in SMA medium and the disease symptoms that developed were identical to those of the original cadavers gathered at the start. The

Pathogenicity of *Aspergillus terreus* to the rice grasshopper.

Treatment	Percent mortality due to mycosis ($\bar{X} \pm SD$) ^a
Fungal spore suspension	85.4 \pm 2.9 ^{**b}
Water (control)	17.9 \pm 6.9

^an = 3 replicates, 10 insects per replicate. ^b** Significantly different from control (P<0.01) by LSD test.

pathogenicity of the fungus thus was positive.

The fungus was identified as *Aspergillus terreus* Thom. So far

A. terreus has been known to be a soil fungus of the rice ecosystem and this is the first time it has been observed as an insect pathogen. The presence of the spores in the air of the rice ecosystem made it possible for the fungus to infect the rice grasshopper.

Fungus incidence peaked during the first half of Feb 1996 at Annamalai-nagar, which coincided with the maximum field population of the grasshopper (8-10 nymphs or adults net sweep⁻¹). Nearly 6-8 diseased grasshoppers were detected on the leaf

lamina of rice plants at four locations randomly selected in the field. Climatic factors, such as 95% relative humidity and temperatures of 30 °C (max) and 24 °C (min), may have promoted the fungal infection.

Because of its field adaptability and high infectivity, *A. terreus* appears to be a potential candidate for developing a "mycoinsecticide" to biologically control grasshoppers in the future.

The CAB International Mycological Institute in London identified the fungus. ■

Integrated pest management — weeds

Weed control practices for improving N use efficiency and productivity of flood-prone lowland rice

A. Ghosh and A. R. Sharma, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack 753006, India

Flood-prone lowland rice in eastern India is mostly dry-sown through broadcasting seeds on poorly prepared fields, a practice resulting in early weed infestation and inefficient use of basally applied fertilizers. Nitrogen use efficiency can be improved by controlling weeds through off-season tillage operations and adopting mechanical or chemical methods in the early stages.

We investigated the effects of tillage, weed control practices, and N fertilizer on the performance of rice during 1994 at Cuttack, India. A split-plot design,

Daily variations in flooding patterns in the field during the growing period of rice. Arrows indicate dates of sowing (s), germination (g), beushani/transplanting (t), and harvesting (h) of rice. Cuttack, India.

with tillage in main plots and combinations of weed control and N fertilizer in subplots, was used in three replications. The crop was grown in plots plowed in summer (Mar) and/or before sowing (late May) or transplanting (late July) (conventional tillage) with or without basal application of 40 kg N ha⁻¹. The crop was sown in dry soil on 1 Jun using 400 seeds m⁻² at 20-cm row spacing, and sprayed with thiobencarb at 2 kg ha⁻¹ within a week of sowing or subjected to beushani at 42 d after water accumulated in the field. Puddling was also included as an additional treatment for comparison, where 42-d-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing using 3-4 seedlings hill⁻¹. Gayatri, a semidwarf, long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive rice variety, was used in the experiment.

Seeds germinated with the monsoon showers. Water started accumulating in the field from mid-July onward following regular monsoon showers (see figure). Water depth fluctuated widely, rising from 0 cm at 22 d after germination (DAG) to 54 cm at 36 DAG and receding to 0 cm at 52 DAG. The crops subjected to beushani or transplanted at 42 DAG at 12 cm water depth established well because the water level remained <10 cm up to 20 d thereafter. Peak flooding of 60 cm occurred in the late vegetative growth stages (78-84 DAG) and the crop

experienced extreme excess water stress for 10 d. Water level showed a declining trend from September and had receded completely by late October.

Yield performance of rice was poor because of inadequate crop stand. Excessive flooding at both early and late vegetative stages resulted in restricted tiller production and greater mortality, leading to only 50-70 panicles m⁻² at maturity (Table 1). The mean grain yield was significantly more with summer plowing than with conventional tillage because of the beneficial effect on the number and weight of panicles. Weed control efficiency from summer plowing was 56.3% compared with conventional tillage. The rice plants remained short and produced fewer panicles m⁻² in the unweeded control than when weeds were controlled. Controlling weeds by chemical or mechanical methods improved grain yield significantly. The grain yield was highest with puddling, a practice that was on a par with the direct-sown crop under beushani but significantly higher than chemical weeding. Increase in yield was associated with a decrease in weed dry weight, which was lowest with puddling. The transplanted crop remained virtually weed-free throughout because growing weeds were incorporated thoroughly during puddling, and subsequent higher